

A TECHNICAL REPORT

APPLICATIONS OF GIS IN INFRASTRUCTURE ASSESMENT AND DEVELOPMENT.

**(FOCUS ON
TRANSPORTATION
NETWORK SYSTEM).**

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October 2011

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1.0 INTRODUCTION

GIS which is short for **global information system** and is defined as; “*A system for capturing, storing, checking, integrating, manipulating, analysing and displaying data which are spatially referenced to the Earth*¹”.

This is normally considered to involve a spatially referenced computer database and appropriate applications software. The process involved in this data capture is usually **Remote-Sensing** which has to do with The science (and art) of acquiring information about an object, without entering in contact with it, by sensing and recording reflected or emitted energy and processing, analyzing, and applying that information.

The driving aim for the use of this type of information system is usually to aid decision making, in various fields of endeavour which is helpful because some kind of data cannot be collected or even analysed without such medium as remote sensing.

The field of interest determines the type of data that would be captured and the way it would be analyzed and applied. This implies that Remotely Sensed data has applications in various disciplines, hence the term **Inter-Disciplinary** which is usually used to refer to GIS.

The aim of this study therefore is to discuss the use of GIS in **Infrastructure Assessment(transportation infrastructure)** as one of the possible fields of GIS application. We shall commence with chapter One, by explaining what elements make up the Infrastructure of a locality or place, after which we shall see how GIS can be applied in proper and more accurate decision making for the selected branch of infrastructure (**transportation**) in chapter two. In Chapter three we shall conclude by drawing deductions in the form of a general appraisal, from the study and finally making recommendations towards more efficient use of the global information system in the 21st century.

1.2.0 COMPONENTS OF INFRASTRUCTURE

The Merriam Webster dictionary defines infrastructure as “*the system of public works of a country, state or region, also the resources such as personnel, buildings and equipment required for an activity*”^[2]

It can also be defined as : “*the basic physical and organizational structures needed for the operation of a society or enterprise,*”^[3] or the services and facilities necessary for an economy to function.

It is typically used to refer to the technical structures that support a society, such as roads, water supply, sewers, electrical grids, telecommunications, and so forth, and can be defined as "the physical components of interrelated systems providing commodities and services essential to enable, sustain, or enhance societal living conditions."^[4]

There has been controversies however regarding the true components of the term infrastructure as is typically used in urban design and city planning.

A more integrative definition therefore was arrived at by the **US National Research Council panel** which sought to clarify the situation by adopting the term "public works infrastructure", referring to:

"... both specific functional modes – highways, streets, roads, and bridges; mass transit; airports and airways; water supply and water resources; wastewater management; solid-waste treatment and disposal; electric power generation and transmission; telecommunications; and hazardous waste management – and the combined system these modal elements comprise. A comprehension of infrastructure spans not only these public works facilities, but also the operating procedures, management practices, and development policies that interact together with societal demand and the physical world to facilitate the transport of people and goods, provision of water for drinking and a variety of other uses, safe disposal of society's waste products, provision of energy where it is needed, and transmission of information within and between communities."^[5]

Thus we understand that GIS can be applied in the maintenance of the various components of a city's infrastructure .

1.3.0 Classification of infrastructure

In his article titled '*Infrastructure In India*', which was published in the topical essay section of the ICFAI journal of Infrastructure, Deepak Kumar, explains the classification of a city's infrastructure into HARD infrastructure and SOFT infrastructure. In this article, "hard" infrastructure refers to the large physical networks necessary for the functioning of a modern industrial nation, whereas "soft" infrastructure refers to all the institutions which are required to maintain the economic, health, and cultural and social standards of a country, such as the financial system, the education system, the health care system, the system of government, and law enforcement, as well as emergency services.^[6]

Our study however focuses on study of this *hard infrastructure* which includes the following;

1. Transportation Network.
2. Water supply pipelines.
3. Power and tele-communications distribution network.
4. Waste management system.

It should suffice to say that, the use of GIS in assessment of these elements, is a topic that is widely discussed and even employed in today's management world, and one would expect their applications to be discussed here, but because of definiteness of scope and constraint of time we shall be discussing the use of GIS in **Transportation network** only.

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CHAPTER TWO

TRANSPORTATION INFRASTRUCTURE.

2.1.0 INTRODUCTION

Chicago transit authority control tower.

Photo;wiki commons.

Every infrastructure manager or developer understands that it is not a small task at all. Many cities and urban areas have infrastructure constructed years ago which have no accurate plans and record. Even when the managers know what is there, they usually lack proper knowledge of what condition it is in. Even where theses exist, there are no generally accepted basis for the asset evaluation and decision making.

The development and adoption of GIS technology is helping to overcome these problems and the transportation industry has not been left out of this blessing thus GIS finds applications in this field also.

2.2.0 THE APPLICATIONS

In recent times, GIS applications in transportation has been widely explored and in fact a specific branch of GIS applied to transportation issues, commonly labeled as **GIS-T**, has emerged.

Geographic Information Systems for Transportation (GIS-T) refers to the principles and applications of applying geographic information technologies to transportation problems [Miller and Shaw, 2001].

⁽¹⁾According to (Shaw,2001); the study of the applications of GIS in transportation can be approached from three perspectives;

- **Data representations.** How the various components of transport systems can be represented in a GIS-T?
- **Analysis and modeling.** How the transport methodologies can be used in a GIS-T?
- **Applications.** What types of applications are particularly suitable for GIS-T?

This can be illustrated using the diagram below:

Diagram: 'the geography of transport systems' copyright © 1998-2011, Dr. Jean-Paul Rodrigue, Dept. of Global Studies & Geography, Hofstra University.

The above illustration explains that first, there has to be a collection of data from the source, and subsequent encoding into a system, which has to be well represented in space and in

attribute. then the data has to be managed, this stage involves organizing the data according to spatial, schematic and temporal data. The third stage, is the analysis of the data, through query and answer, and thus arrangement into a desired format which is ready to be presented for reports and to aid decision making.

2.2.1 APPLICATIONS OF GIS FOR VEHICLE ROUTING.

The depot manager faces the task of designing routes (such as those shown below) for his delivery vehicles and this problem of route design is known as the *vehicle routing* or *vehicle scheduling* problem.

Fig.01: Distribution of customers around a depot.(illustration; author).

Hence the vehicle routing problem can be defined as the problem of designing routes for delivery vehicles (of known capacities) which are to operate from a single depot to supply a set of

customers with known locations and known demands for a certain commodity. Routes for the vehicles are designed to minimise some objective such as the total distance travelled.

Using the distribution of schools and residences in the state of Qatar, as case study, nick named **Al-Hady Vehicle Routing Application**, Moines El Shafey and M. A. Nasimudheen, explains the possibility of using GIS to solve this vehicle routing problem.

In the study, A variety of buses, different types and capacities, are used for transporting students to schools and back. On an average there are eight buses associated with every school. Now a days, most of the families are sending their children by buses because houses are spread out than before and Ministry of Education (MOE) has to meet this growing demand by either buy or rent new buses. Optimizing the cost of operations is not available because each school has to find, manually, the best route for each bus based on student addresses and bus capacity.

To handle any changes in the pick up & drop off point manually, sometimes on a daily basis, is not an easy task thus Automating the routing decisions is the solution in order to maximize the potential use of each bus, minimize costs, and provide a more effective method of reallocating routes due to emergencies.^[9]

Salient Features Of This Application.

The application works in the form of a wizard which takes the user through a set of easy steps and at the end efficient bus routes are generated. At every stage data validation and checks are done in order to ensure that only valid data is entered and no inconsistencies are resulted. Interface is provided using Visual Basic and Map Object.

Generates routes to handle many-to-many situations. Most of the real life routing situations involve many-to-many situations where many vehicles are serving many demand points. Typically in these situations two decisions are to be made i. e. The demand points to be served by each vehicle and The sequence of visiting demand points. ArcView Network Analyst handles only one-to-many situations but Al Hady has customized ArcView Network Analyst in order to handle many-to-many situations.

- * Routes can be generated based on Least Cost or Shortest Path criteria
- * Buses of different capacities are used for transporting students. The number of students in the buses are not allowed to exceed their capacities.
- * User friendly interface for digitizing drop off/ pick up points:
Stops can be digitized from GPS data. A user friendly interface for digitizing stops with map interface with editing capability is provided.
- * Route constrains are taken care of, Closed roads and one way roads are all taken care of, Turn impedance and traversing costs are also included.

Step 1: Data Collection.

These are the four sets of information that has been collected for the two schools

1. Student Data;

Student names, ID numbers, Addresses and Telephone numbers are collected from the schools.

2. Traffic Data;

Four maps for the Catchment area of the School was created. Two student collected the required data (Way Roads, Turning Restriction, Number of Lanes, Speed Limits) in three Days.

3. Intersection Data;

Thirteen major intersections (Traffic Signals and Roundabouts) are used to collect the average time taken along with the average number of vehicles crossing each part of it. Two groups of the students collected these data in seven days.

4. Digitizing the actual route;

Four maps of the catchment area of the school was created. Students followed the actual bus routes and later digitized the routes. In case of Al Rayyan Al Jaddid school digitizing the actual route as well as the pick up points were done using GPS.

ROUTE WIZARD

Al Hady works in the form of a wizard which takes the user through a set of easy steps and at the end efficient routes are generated. The steps involved are the following

- * Selection of interface (English/Arabic)
- * Selection of school. User can select the school either by location or by name.
- * Selection of stops file (pick up/ drop off points). At this point user can opt for creating a new file

by using GPS data or on screen digitization. User can also edit the existing stop file.

- * Selection of objective i.e. least cost or least distance.

Least distance route need not be the least cost route. Cost information has been collected and stored in feature attribute tables and turn tables.

- * Digitization of road closures/ openings

User can select street and with the click of a button can set the rules of road.

- * Selection of buses

- * Allocation of drop off/ pick up points to different buses.

This can be done automatically where in a sophisticated algorithm will take care of efficiently assigning the stops to different buses. User can also manually assign stops to various buses.

- * Generation of routes.

fig 01b; Generated Routing paths.

Results

Results of the application are very encouraging. During test running it could generate routes which are 33% more efficient than the previous routes. Estimated savings by national level implementation of the project is US\$ 8 Million.

Al Hady Decision Support System for Vehicle Routing is very generic in nature and can be extended

for many similar situations. Examples are garbage collection, network planning, water distribution in suburbs and commercial goods transfer.

2.2.2 APPLICATIONS OF GIS FOR TRANSPORTATION SAFETY ANALYSIS.

It has been found that Using appropriate GIS software, it is possible to ascertain the degree or level of safety of a given transportation network.

In a study carried out by Sudeshna Mitra,(PhD), Assistant Professor at the Civil and Environmental Engineering Department, California Polytechnic State University, San Luis Obispo, he developed a GIS based methodology for fatal, injury and pedestrian crash cluster mapping and analysis using crash data and various spatial, demographic and socioeconomic data available from a real city in the USA. The cluster detection in this study used readily available spatial autocorrelation tools in GIS to identify crash clusters.^[2]

Fig.02: Distribution of crash clusters with schools and bars and pubs.

As a result, this method is straightforward to apply but at the same time accurate in meaning that crash clusters are not just detected by frequency or crash concentration/density but by investigating the spatial correlation of the crash attributes. Statistical significance of these created clusters is also checked with Z-statistics. Once these clusters are mapped, subjective judgments are used to detect clusters that are associated with spatial attributes such as schools, bars and pubs, population density, age distribution and poverty data.

Figure 3: Crash clusters with population density, schools, and bars and pubs.

Figure 4: Crash clusters by drivers age 24 and under with density of persons age 24 and under, schools, and bars and pubs.

The output map analysis indicates that there are some correlations with school locations and pedestrian crashes as well as bars and pubs with minor and severe crashes related to

vehicles. In addition some common patterns of higher number of minor and severe injury clusters are observed across locations with high density populations, but correlation with socio-economic distribution such as percentage of people below poverty or age distribution are not very significant.

Once these maps are created and checked, they may help local transportation agencies to understand issues of fatal, injury and pedestrian crashes so that further site specific investigations are possible to **enhance safety**.

2.2.3 Applications Of GIS For travel demand analysis

fig 05: microscopic model of the travel demand over a given area. Geodata solutions inc. (c)2008.

Travel demand analyses are useful for transportation planning and policy development in a study area. However, travel demand modeling faces two obstacles. First, standard practice solves the four travel components (trip generation, trip distribution, modal split and network assignment) in a sequential manner. This can result in inconsistencies and non-convergence. Second, the data required are often complex and difficult to manage. Recent advances in formal methods for network equilibrium-based travel demand modeling and computational platforms for spatial data handling can overcome these obstacles. This paper reports on the development of a prototype geographic information system (GIS) design to support network equilibrium-based travel demand models.

For example, the average passenger demand at an airport over a given period of time could be ascertained by plotting the map of the various flight paths entering and leaving the airport over the said time and also knowing the capacity of the individual planes.

A case study of such application was carried out at the phoenix-mesa gateway Airport, in the city of mesa, Arizona; where the various flight paths densities, for all jets and helicopters; and area of overlaying airport facilities were plotted using different color codes as shown below;

PRINT AND INSERT

fig.06: phoenix-mesa airport flight paths.

Proper planning of the surrounding area can ensure continued growth of the airport operations and serve as a catalyst for further economic development of the city of Mesa. By analyzing these flight patterns using ARCGIS spatial analyst (a leading GIS software), appropriate land uses can be identified where airport operations would have the least impact.^[3]

2.2.4 Applications Of GIS For Traffic Monitoring And Control

The Highway Agency in the UK and many other countries monitor ongoing traffic at critical points in the road network round-the-clock, using cameras, counting devices or other means of traffic data gathering, and then relaying this information to the public or using it for analytical purposes.

Fig 07; Real time satellite photo showing the positions of traffic lights. *(Source;Kitsap County Public Works).*

Traffic control systems are among the most demanding of the Intelligent Transportation Systems. They may have to cover large geographical areas and interface with a large number of devices, thus managing data available from a variety of disparate sources, not necessarily in common format. (WS Atkins, 1999). Metronetworks is a private UK company that specializes in relaying traffic information, giving up-to-date real-time traffic information to the public, to be broadcasted via radio or to be displayed on the Internet.

Southampton has implemented a EU-funded project, ROMANSE. In this project, relevant up-to-date traffic and travel information for public and private transport users is posted electronically on touch screen displays at main transport interchanges, shopping centres, tourist information centres and libraries, and also on the Internet./p>

Trafficmaster is a company in the UK that has been going its own way, installing a network of traffic flow sensors along major road arteries, and relaying this information to subscribing motorists via mobile phone or in-car voice device.^[4] (Fitzgibbon, 1999). These type of gadgets obviously employ the use of remote sensing in acquiring relevant real-time information and after relaying it to a workstation from where it could be analysed and sent out to the road users,traffic wardens etc.

2.2.5 Applications Of GIS For Vehicle Tracking And Dispatching.

Not only is finding the best way from A to B of importance to vehicle drivers or the company who deploys them. To keep track of where the vehicle is at any given moment of time is equally, if not even more crucial, in efficient fleet management. Tracking and monitoring of vehicle movements emerged with the advances in mobile communication (GSM) and satellite navigation (GPS). The position of a vehicle is monitored via onboard GPS, transmitted back to a base via GSM, and loaded into a GIS where it can be displayed on map.

Fig 08: Fleet vehicle GPS tracking mechanism.(source:Dale Perry).^[5]

Fig.09: GPS Real-time object location mechanism. *(source:Dale Perry).^[5]*

The Global Positioning System (GPS) is a constellation of 24 satellites, which provide information to a GPS receiver, so that software in the receiver can determine a position in three dimensions (altitude, latitude, and longitude). There are two types of GPS tracking: passive and real time. A passive GPS tracker will record travel activities and positions, which can be downloaded to a computer. A real time GPS tracking system will show its position, live.^[5]

Already in 1995, Oslo Taxi of Oslo, Norway, fully automated the monitoring of its entire fleet (Baumann, 1995). The exact location of all vehicles is now known at all times by the taxi dispatchers, improving any needed emergency response to the driver and customer response to incoming orders, ensuring that the nearest available taxi is sent to the pickup location.

Around 400,000 vehicles are stolen each year in the UK. With an in-car GPS that continuously relays the car's position to a control centre, the car can easily be tracked in case it is stolen. In case of an emergency breakdown, help can be dispatched to his or her exact location. (Fitzgibbon, 1999).

2.2.6 Applications Of GIS For Site Selection And Service Area Analysis

Service area is the term used to describe a region surrounding a network location within which its services are reachable and accessible. For example, the 20-minute service area for a network location (such as a fire station) includes all the streets that can be reached within 20 minutes from that location. In ArcGIS Network Analyst, a type of network analysis for determining the region that encompasses all accessible streets (streets that lie within a specified impedance).^[6]

A casestudy of Portland's metro bus system, conducted by Andy Smith-Petersen, University of Southern Maine,^[7] to determine the areas of the city served within ¼ mile (roughly five minutes' walk) of each bus stop along with some corresponding demographics and also to identify potential new areas for service proves how helpful, ArcGIS network analyst(software) could be in analysing the service area of a given transportation network.

step 1: Creating A Straight-Line Buffer.

step 2: Building The Network Data Sets.

step 3: Solving The Service Area.

step 4: The Network Service Area.

Step 5: The Metro Service Area

This information which has been generated with help of a GIS software, could be further processed to show in percentages the mainland area metro coverage, including buildings, population and parcels of land within the service area. This could be achieved using already existing data obtained from census and transportation agencies or bureau in the state.

Below is an illustration of such analysis;

Fig.10-14:service area analysis of Portland’s metro bus system.(Andy Smith-Petersen).^[7]

If such information is in turn made available to relevant transport agencies or bureau, they could come up with a need index which would readily expose ill-served areas and the degrees of ill-service and by so doing better distribution decisions could be made.

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CHAPTER THREE

3.1.0 CONCLUSION

The GIS design has several key features, including:

- (i) Realistic representation of the multimodal transportation network,
- (ii) Increased likelihood of database integrity after updates,
- (iii) Effective user interfaces,
- (iv) Efficient implementation of network equilibrium solution algorithms.

These, together with relevant professional expertise, combine to give unending solutions to various transportation related issues.

In conclusion, we agree that, GIS has many obvious advantages over the traditional manual methods of geographic data analysis; this can be in terms of speed of work, clarity of presentation, convenience of work, consistency in details, ease of accessibility, broader interface for data processing, improved information sharing, increased productivity, ease of update.etc. These are issues which are still under review by scholars and information professionals worldwide, and being adopted in most businesses, and industries of which transportation is a huge benefactor.

3.2.0 RECOMMENDATIONS

- GIS transportation database creators users should be professionals drawn from all relevant fields as it integrates several individual subjects. such as demography, the need for professionalism in handling of these data is expedient.
- Learning time of GIS which is usually quite long could also be reduced if appropriate professionals are employed.
- Continuous and scheduled update of GIS transport database should be carried out to ensure continuity and availability of real-time data always.